

MCM-41 as novel solid phase sorbent for the pre-concentration of pesticides in environmental waters and determination by microflow liquid chromatography-quadrupole linear ion trap mass spectrometry

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The present work describes a novel solid phase extraction method based on the MCM-41 sorbent for the pre-concentration of eight pesticides with different polarity (including organophosphates, carbamates and triazoles) in environmental waters. A microflow liquid chromatography-quadrupole linear ion trap mass spectrometer was used for the determination and extra-confirmation of the pesticides in the water. Variables affecting the retention (pH and ionic strength) and elution (type and volume elution solvent) of the analytes, the sorbent amount and the breakthrough volume were optimized. The effect of the matrix components in the response of the pesticides was investigated in two types of environmental water (river and dam waters). Signal suppression, which was found in all cases depends on the analyte and the kind of the sample; therefore, quantification was carried out using the standard addition approach. Detection and quantification limits achieved in environmental samples were lower than $0.01 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and $0.05 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively (with the exception of cymoxanil in dam water, which showed a quantitation limit of $0.16 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). Accuracy and precision in environmental samples, at two concentration levels, ranged from 65% to 126% (relative standard deviation $\leq 14\%$), except for methomyl with recoveries lower than 60%. The method developed herein was applied to the analysis of several environmental waters from Spain in which pesticides were not found in any case. Diffusion NMR methods and ^{13}C CP/MAS NMR were applied in order to establish that MCM-41 selectively interacts in different extent with pesticides of different polarity such as cymoxanil or phosalone.

1. Introduction

The banned organochlorine pesticides were replaced by organophosphorous (OPPs) pesticides and organonitrogen pesticides (ONPs), which are widely applied because of their ability to combat a large number of pests, among other advantages. ONPs term cover a large number of pesticides, carbamate among them.

OPPs and carbamates interfere with the acetylcholine-mediated synaptic transmission in the nervous systems via inhibition of the acetylcholinesterase enzyme activity. Exposure to water contaminated with these substances is harmful to the health and the life of humans and to all aquatic living organisms [1–7].

Fungicides play a crucial role in modern agriculture and act by either inhibiting sterol biosynthesis, energy production, amino acid synthesis, cell division or multiple sites of action [8]. Whereas fungicides are designed to control fungal pathogens, their modes of action are not specific to fungi in such a way that they will be toxic to a wide range of organisms.

These pesticides have a moderate to high water solubility and are, therefore, capable of transportation into aquatic systems via surface runoff, their mobility depending on K_{foc} [9].

The determination of OPPs and carbamates in environmental water samples has been reviewed by Tankiewicz et al. [10]; and of fungicides in biological and environmental matrices by Cserhádi et al. [11].

The use of solid phase extraction (SPE) with C18 or styrene-divinylbenzene copolymers has been the most frequent choice [12] for preparation of environmental water samples. However, some tendencies have recently appeared related to novel sorbents for SPE, which have been summarized in some reviews [13,14].

Recently, a new family of ordered mesoporous silicas has gained great interest in sample preparation because of their large pores (from 2 to 10 nm), high surface areas (above 1000 m²/g) and tunable surface properties. The most commonly used MCM-41, MCM-48 or MCM-50 (MCM = Mobil Composition of Matter) possesses hexagonal, cubic or meso-lamellar phases, respectively, whereas SBA-15 shows large pore hexagonal phase (SBA = Santa Barbara Amorphous).

In a review, Zhao et al. [15] compiled the use of mesoporous materials in sample preparation for extraction of metals ions (MCM-41), adsorption of volatile organic compounds (MCM-41 and MCM-48) or trinitrotoluene in aqueous contaminated soil samples, also providing some interesting conclusions: (i) they offer different physicochemical properties in surface area and pore structure as well as versatile availability in surface functionalization to provide hydrophobic, hydrophilic, positively and negatively charged surface to interact with analytes and (ii) the combination of the size-exclusion effect of mesopores against big size molecules and the adsorption of small size analytes inside the mesopores mimics the effect of multidimensional chromatographic separations.

In addition, a hierarchically imprinted SBA-15 polymer was prepared and used in SPE for detecting bisphenol A in spiked water samples [16].

SBA-15 and a spherical mesoporous silica (SM), functionalized with C18 (SBA-15-C18 and SM-C18) and no functionalized were examined as sorbents for SPE of 17 β -estradiol in aqueous media [17] and the adsorption capacity of SBA-15 bi-functionalized with C18 and aminopropyl groups (SBA-15-C18-NH₂) was evaluated versus twelve endocrine disrupting compounds in water and compared with a commercial phase [18].

However, these applications are devoted to a comprehensive optimization of the extraction procedure, but with a limited method validation.

Recently, we have reported the use of raw MCM-41 as sorbent in SPE, to pre-concentrate fourteen pharmaceuticals of very different polarity in surface waters [19]. This work describes a simple and inexpensive SPE technique which involves the first use of the MCM-41 combined with microflow LC-MS/MS. It is worth to note that good recoveries were obtained using this sorbent, which avoided derivatization processes of the material and, consequently, involved a save of time and costs.

As for pesticides, BHC, epoxide, endosulfan, aldrin, dieldrin, endosulfan sulfate, DDE, DDD, DDT, methoxychlor and 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid have been removed from water samples using mesoporous silica, mesoporous silica-encapsulated Fe₃O₄ or cyclodextrin-functionalized mesoporous silica [20], but, to the best of our knowledge, these sorbents have not been applied as SPE sorbent to pre-concentrate pesticides in water samples.

Although LC-MS² techniques, such as triple quadrupole (QqQ) and ion trap (IT) are routinely used in environmental analysis, more recent approaches in LC-MS², the hybrid quadrupole-linear ion trap (QqLIT) among them, are being increasingly used. This allows very powerful scan runs which can be combined in one single experiment when performing information-dependent data acquisition (IDA) [21].

The goal of this paper was to check the MCM-41 as a new sorbent to pre-concentrate eight pesticides of different polarity including OPPs insecticides (methidathion, parathion-methyl, malathion, phosalone and diazinon), fungicides (cymoxanil and penconazole) and one carbamate (methomyl) from environmental waters and to take advantage of the improvements in sensitivity and specificity provided by the microflow LC-QqLIT for quantitation and confirmation of the above mentioned pesticides. The applicability of this approach was tested on water samples collected in two different environmental sites from Almería (Spain), where contamination with pesticides could be expected.

2. Experimental

2.1. Reagents and standards

All chemicals used in the present work were of analytical grade. LC-grade acetonitrile and methanol solvents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany), dichloromethane, *n*-hexane, acetone were obtained from Panreac (Spain), hydrochloric acid (HCl, 37%), ammonium hydroxide (NH₃, 25%) and ethanol (EtOH, 96%) were purchased from J.T. Backer (The Netherlands), ammonium acetate (NH₄OAc) was purchased from Riedel-de Haën (Seelze, Germany) and potassium chloride (KCl) was provided by Merck (Germany). Ultrapure water was obtained from a Milli-Q water purification system from Millipore (USA).

For the synthesis of MCM-41 material, tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) were used, both purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. The 3 mL syringe body of polypropylene and two frits of polyethylene, both of them used for packing the MCM-41 sorbent, were from Supelco (USA).

Analytical standards (>99% purity) of methomyl (MET), cymoxanil (CYM), methidathion (METH), malathion (MAL), penconazole (PEN), diazinon (DIA), parathion-methyl (PMT) and phosalone (PHO) were purchased from Riedel-de Haën (Seelze, Germany). Table S1, in the Electronic Supplementary Material (EMS), shows the chemical structure and physicochemical properties of target compounds.

Individual analytical standard solutions of the target pesticides (1000 mg L⁻¹) were prepared by weighing and dissolving the corresponding solid standard in acetonitrile. These solutions were protected against light and stored at 4 °C, being stable for at least 3 months under these conditions. Working standard solutions of pesticides were prepared daily by appropriate dilution of their individual stock standard solutions in acetonitrile-ultrapure water (10:90, v/v).

Deuterium oxide (D₂O, 99.9%_D), deuterium chloride (DCI, 99.0%_D) and acetonitrile-d₃ (CD₃CN, 99.8%_D) were used for diffusion NMR experiments. All of them were purchased from Eurisotop (France).

2.2. Microflow LC-QqLIT-MS procedure

The chromatographic analysis of pesticides was performed in an Agilent 1200 LC (Agilent Technologies, CA, USA) provided with a binary pump and connected to a hybrid triple quadrupole/Linear Ion Trap (QqLIT) mass spectrometer system (5500 QTRAP® LC/MS/MS from Applied Biosystems Sciex Instruments (Foster City, CA, USA). LC pesticides separation was achieved with a ZORBAX Eclipse XDB C8 (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm particle size) from Agilent using as mobile phase a mixture of acetonitrile as eluent A and LC-grade water containing 0.1% formic acid as eluent B. The elution gradient program started with 10% A for 0.5 min, increasing to 100% A in 9 min, maintained 5 min in this conditions and finally 0.1 min to return to initial conditions. Then, the column was re-equilibrated for 10 min before the next injection. The flow rate of the mobile phase was set constant at 0.4 mL min⁻¹ and the injection volume was 10 μL.

The microflow LC system was connected to a QqLIT-MS with an ESI interface and was operated in positive ionization (PI) mode. The Turbo Ion Spray source settings were: IonSprayVoltage (IS) 5500 V, Source Temperature (TEM) 500 °C, Curtain Gas (CUR) 30 psi, Collision Gas (CAD) Medium, both Ion Source Gas 1 (GS1) and Ion Source Gas 2 (GS2) 50 psi. Nitrogen was used as the nebulizer gas, curtain gas and collision gas.

The determination of pesticides was performed in the multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) mode, recording the precursor ion and the two most abundant product ions for each analyte. In order to obtain the maximum sensitivity for identification and detection of all target compounds the operational MS/MS parameters for each pesticide such as declustering potential (DP), entrance potential (EP) for precursor ions, collision energy (CE) and collision cell exit potential (CXP) were optimized by direct infusion of individual standard solutions of each pesticide at 1 mg L⁻¹ in methanol. Selected reaction monitoring (SRM)

experiments were recorded by using the Scheduled MRM option, setting the target scan time at 1 s, a MRM detection window of 40 s and with Q1 set at low resolution and Q3 at one unit.

For extra confirmation of the pesticides, an IDA method was programmed combining SRM as survey scan and an enhanced product ion scan (EPI) as dependent scan in the same injection. The main SRM transition for each compound was recorded and 8 transitions were monitored in PI mode. Regarding the IDA criteria, the intensity threshold was set to 500 cps and without exclusion after dynamic background subtraction of the survey scan. EPI scans were recorded at DP = 100 V at one collision energy value CE = 25 V, but using the collision energy spread (CES = 5 V) and the LIT scanning from 80 to 450 amu at a scan rate of 10,000 amu/s. The dynamic fill-time option was selected on the ion trap and EPI scans were monitored in each SRM-IDA-EPI cycle, being the complete SRM-IDA-EPI cycle time of 1.58 s. The complete SRM-IDA-EPI cycle time was 1.58 s.

2.3. Synthesis and characterization of homogeneous MCM-41

The MCM-41 was synthesized according to a method previously developed by Grün et al. [22]. The mesoporous silica material was prepared by dissolving of 2.5 g of CTAB with 50 g of deionized water. Then 13.2 g of ammonium hydroxide (25%) and 60.0 g of absolute ethanol (96%) were added and the surfactant solution was stirred for 15 min at 250 rpm. Next, 4.7 g of TEOS were added at one time resulting a white gel with the following molar composition: 1TEOS:0.3CTAB:11NH₃:144H₂O:58EtOH. The gel was stirred for 2 h at 250 rpm and then the solid product was filtered and washed with 100 mL of deionized water and 100 mL of methanol under vacuum and was dried overnight at 363 K. Finally, the solid was calcined at 823 K in a furnace for 5 h in order to remove the surfactant template.

The characterization of the synthesized MCM-41 was performed by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), scanning transmission microscopy (STEM) and Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms.

The X-ray powder diffraction patterns were obtained on an EMPYREAN PANanalytical spectrometer using the Cu K α radiation and operating at 45 kV and 40 mA within the 2 θ range of 0.7 and 10 $^\circ$ and with 0.01 2 θ steps. The sample was placed between two films of kapton.

The SEM micrographs were obtained on a JEOL JSM-6490LV Scanning Electron Microscope after coating the sample with a 20 nm thickness gold film, using a voltage 20 kV.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were obtained on a FEI Talos F200X TEM/STEM electron microscope, operating at 200 kV. The samples were crushed in an agate mortar, dispersed in ethanol and pouring a single drop onto a formvar-carbon film covered copper grid. The STEM mode allows working in mode HAADF (high-angle annular dark-field), ADF (annular dark-field), dark field (DF) and BF (bright field) and the corresponding images were obtained in TEM, HR-TEM and HAADF-STEM modes.

Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms were measured at 77 K using an ASAP 2420 volumetric adsorption analyzer (Micromeritics). Prior to adsorption measurements, the samples were outgassed at 400 $^\circ$ C in a nitrogen flow for 6 h. The surface area was obtained by the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method using adsorption data in the relative pressure range from 0.05 to 0.2. The pore size distribution was calculated from the adsorption branch of the isotherm using the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) model.

2.4. Solid phase extraction procedure

SPE cartridges packed with 100 mg of synthesized MCM-41 sorbent were prepared in the laboratory using a 3 mL polypropylene syringe and two polyethylene frits to retain the material sorbent. Each SPE cartridge was conditioned with 5 mL of acetonitrile and 5 mL of ultrapure water adjusted to pH 4.0 \pm 0.1. Immediately, 100 mL of water sample

(pH 4.0 \pm 0.1) containing 0.01 mol L⁻¹ KCl were passed through the SPE cartridge at 5 mL min⁻¹ flow rate using a Büchi VacV 500 (Switzerland) vacuum pump, connected to an extraction manifold from Waters (USA). Next, the MCM-41 sorbent was dried for 5 min with air and for 5 min with N₂ and, then, the pesticides were eluted with 7 mL of acetonitrile. The extract was evaporated to dryness under a stream of N₂ and reconstituted in 1 mL acetonitrile:water (10:90, v/v). Finally, the extract solution was filtered through a filter of 0.2 μ m particle size and 10 μ L were injected in the microflow LC-QqLIT-MS.

2.5. Real water samples

In this study, two types of environmental water samples (river and dam waters) were used for evaluation of the MCM-41 as the sorbent for pre-concentration of eight pesticides. The river water sample (RW) was collected from Nacimiento River and the dam water sample (DW) was picked up in a dam whose water came from the Andarax River and is used to irrigate crops, both samples are located in Almería (Spain).

Real water samples were collected using 1 L amber bottles, with Teflon lined caps, which were previously rinsed with the sample water on site, and they were transported immediately to the laboratory. Both, river and dam samples were filtered through a 0.45 μ m cellulose filter, and then, the filtered samples were stored at 4 $^\circ$ C in a refrigerator for a maximum of 2 days to minimize microbial degradation before analysis.

2.6. NMR methods

2.6.1. Diffusion NMR experiments in solids

Solid state ¹³C (100.73 MHz) CPMAS NMR spectra were obtained on a Bruker WB 400 spectrometer at 300 K using a 4 mm DVT probehead. Three samples corresponding to MCM-41 alone, and MCM-41 after SPE of PHO or CYM, were carefully packed in a 4-mm diameter cylindrical zirconia rotors with Kel-F end-caps. Operating conditions involved 2.9 μ s 90 $^\circ$ ¹H pulses and decoupling field strength of 86.2 kHz by SPINAL 64 sequence. ¹³C spectra were originally referenced to a glycine sample and then the chemical shifts were recalculated to the Me₄Si (for the carbonyl atom δ (glycine) = 176.1 ppm). The acquisition parameters for ¹³C CPMAS were: spectral width, 40 kHz; recycle delay, 5 s; acquisition time, 30 ms; contact time, 2 ms; spin rate, 12 kHz and ns 49,000.

2.6.2. Diffusion NMR experiments in solution

All measurements were performed on a Bruker Avance III 500 spectrometer equipped with a microprocessor-controlled gradient unit and a third radiofrequency channel using an indirect 5 mm TBI ¹H/³¹P/BB triple probe with an actively shielded Z-gradient coil. The spectral reference used was internal tetramethylsilane for ¹H. All experiments were run without spinning to avoid convection. The standard Bruker pulse program, step1s, employing a stimulated echo sequence with monopolar pulses and 1 spoil gradient was utilized. Gradient recovery delays were set to 0.2 ms [23]. A sine shape was used for the gradient pulses and their strength varied automatically in the course of the experiments. The *D* values were determined from the slope of the regression line ln(*I*/*I*₀) versus *G*², according to the following equation [24]

$$\ln\left(\frac{I}{I_0}\right) = -(\gamma\delta)^2\left(\Delta - \frac{\delta}{4}\right)D\frac{4}{\pi^2}G^2$$

where *I*/*I*₀ is the observed spin echo intensity/intensity without gradients, *G* is the gradient strength, Δ is the delay between the midpoints of the gradients, *D* is the diffusion coefficient and δ is the gradient length.

The calibration of the gradients on each spectrometer was carried out via a diffusion measurement of HDO in D₂O at ambient temperature. The *D* value of each sample can then be calculated

according to the following equation, considering that D_{HDO} corresponds to $1.9 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ [25].

$$D = \frac{m_t}{m_{\text{HDO}}} D_{\text{HDO}}$$

The m_t parameter was calculated for each measurement from the observed slope, with the help of the next equation, which takes into account the settings for the diffusion delay Δ , the gradient length δ , as well as the nature of the observed nucleus γ , with respect to the calibration with HDO.

$$m_t = \frac{\text{slope}}{\left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_{\text{HDO}}}\right)^2 \left(\frac{\delta}{\delta_{\text{HDO}}}\right)^2 \frac{\left(\Delta - \frac{\delta}{4}\right)}{\left(\Delta - \frac{\delta}{4}\right)_{\text{HDO}}}}$$

To check reproducibility, three different measurements with different diffusion parameters (δ and/or Δ) were always carried out. The gradient strength was incremented in 4% steps from 8% to 96% so that. The experimental error in D values was estimated to be smaller than $\pm 2\%$. All of the data leading to the reported D values afforded lines whose correlation coefficients were above 0.999 and 12 to 23 points were used for regression analysis. The recovery delay was set to 10 s. The number of scans per increment was 80 and typical experimental times were around 3 h. All diffusion processing and molecular size estimations were performed by using the DiffAtOnce software package [26].

Diffusion NMR experiments were carried out on PHO and CYM pesticide solutions with and without the presence of MCM-41. PHO and CYM solutions without mesoporous material were prepared by mixing 0.5 mL of a solution at $\text{pD} = 2$ (pD was adjusted by adding a diluted solution of deuterium chloride in D_2O) constituted by D_2O and CD_3CN in a 1:1 ratio with 6.4 mg (0.0147 mmol) and 3.5 mg (0.0176 mmol) of PHO and CYM, respectively. The preparation of PHO and CYM samples in presence of MCM-41 was performed by adding 0.6 mg (0.0016 mmol) of PHO and 0.6 mg (0.0030 mmol) of CYM into a solution (0.5 mL) at $\text{pD} = 2$ constituted by D_2O and CD_3CN in a 1:1 ratio and containing 20 mg of MCM-4. In all four cases, the resulting solutions were shaken for 16 h using a Vortex at 1000 rpm, ultrasonicated for 10 min and transferred into NMR tubes for the diffusion NMR analysis.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Optimization of the microflow LC-QqLIT-MS procedure

The microflow LC-QqLIT-MS method used to identify and quantify the target compounds in environmental water samples was developed in a previous work [27] using a hybrid system in which the third quadrupole (Q_3) can operate as a conventional mass filter or as a linear ion trap.

According to the EU requirements (Commission Decision 2002/657/EC) [28] the confirmatory criterion for the analysis of pesticides (included in the Group B) requires at least three identification points. In the SRM method, (i) the retention time (t_R), (ii) one precursor ion, (iii) two ion products and (iv) the ion ratio between them were selected for each pesticide, providing four identification points, which fulfilled the EU requirement.

The most intense transition (SRM1) was used for quantitative purpose while the second one transition (SRM2) was used for identification. Fig. S1 (included in the EMS) shows the chromatograms for the two extracted SRM of the target pesticides.

In addition, in order to avoid false positive findings in the analysis of real samples, other criteria were used for identification: (i) the pesticide t_R in the real sample must be within $\pm 2\%$ the pesticide t_R in the standards and (ii) the relative abundances of the two selected SRM

transitions (SRM2/SRM1) in the real samples must be between $\pm 20\%$ of the SRM2/SRM1 ratios in the analytical standards [29].

Table S2 (included in the EMS) shows the four identifications points. As it can be seen, the abundances of the two selected fragments (SRM1 and SRM2) were similar for most analytes, with ion ratios between 0.3 and 0.84, except for CYM and PHO (ion ratios < 0.3). This is a limitation when identifying these last two compounds at low concentrations in the real samples, given that the presence of the less intense transition (SRM2) has to be verified with an S/N ratio of 3. Therefore, for these two pesticides, the SRM2 transition cannot be used for identification at low concentration levels. This drawback was overcome by the built-in IDA method which combines in the same run SRM and EPI scans, thus obtaining simultaneously accurate quantification and additional structural information [30].

To obtain optimum performance in the IDA mode, the most intense transition (SRM1) was used in the survey scan. The EPI spectra generated for each pesticide were matched against a mass spectral library, the good agreement between the reference spectrum of the library and the spectrum obtained in the samples being given by the fit, reverse fit (RevFit) and purity values provided by the software. The confirmation criteria for identification of the target compounds were a fit value or purity higher than 70%. Fig. S2 (see ESM) show the EPI of each pesticide in the optimized conditions. The IDA approach was programmed for all the analytes, which provided further structural information for confirmation of CYM and PHO (ion ratios < 0.3) as well as extra confirmation for the rest of pesticides.

3.2. Characterization of MCM-41

The XRD patterns of MCM-41 materials prepared in homogeneous medium show several Bragg peaks at low angles between 2.5 and 7.0° 2θ , indexed as (100), (110) and (200) in the hexagonal system (Fig. 1). These peaks are typical of these materials and arise from the quasi-regular arrangement of the mesopores in the bulk material [31]. However, the obtained XRD pattern gave only one broad peak (which can be indexed as 100) and two extremely weak peaks (110 and 200), being indicative of a material which not exhibit long range order [32].

SEM and TEM were used to determine the morphology, shape and size of the particles. The micrographs (Fig. 2.a) show a narrow particle size distribution and well defined spherical particles, as was described by Grün et al. [31], with particle sizes in the range of 0.25 and 1.05 μm (average size 0.65 μm), which is in agreement with the results obtained from TEM (Fig. 2b). HR-TEM and STEM images demonstrated a clear arrangement of hexagonal pores (Fig. 2c and d).

The textural parameters were obtained from N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K. Fig. 3a shows the N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms which are of the type IV according to IUPAC nomenclature [33]. In the region of $p/p_0 > 0.3$ the isotherm is fully reversible, which is characteristic of mesoporous MCM-41 materials. The material exhibits a

Fig. 1. X-ray diffraction pattern obtained of MCM-41.

Fig. 2. (a) SEM, (b) TEM, (c) HRTEM and (d) HAADF-STEM images obtained of MCM-41.

narrow BJH average pore diameter distribution centred at 22.32 Å (Fig. 3b) with a BET surface area of 1095.60 m²/g and BJH cumulative volume of pores of 0.613 cm³/g.

3.3. Optimization of the SPE procedure

The MCM-41 was applied to extract ultra-trace of pesticides from environmental water samples. In order to optimize the extraction conditions, several main parameters including type and volume of solvent

Fig. 3. (a) Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms and (b) BJH pore diameter distribution.

elution, sample pH, ionic strength (salt content), organic modifier, sample flow rate through the SPE cartridge, MCM-41 amount and breakthrough volume were studied in detail.

3.3.1. Selection of solvent eluent

For desorption of pesticides retained onto the MCM-41 sorbent, preliminary studies were performed using 5 mL of different organic solvents such as methanol, acetonitrile, acetone, dichloromethane and *n*-hexane. Aliquots of 25 mL of ultrapure water spiked with 100 ng of the selected pesticides were pre-concentrated into the SPE cartridge containing 50 mg of MCM-41. The sorbent was previously conditioned with 5 mL of the selected elution solvent followed by 5 mL of ultrapure water. The elution of the retained analytes was performed with 5 mL of each organic solvent. As shown in Fig. 4, the worst results were obtained when using *n*-hexane and the best ones when using acetonitrile (between 77.3 and 105.1%), except for MET and CYM (the most polar analytes) whose recoveries were lower than 30%. These low recoveries can be attributed to the high polarity of these pesticides (see Table S1 in ESM), which, in these conditions, were not sufficiently retained onto the sorbent.

Next, the volume of the elution solvent was studied between 5 and 10 mL of acetonitrile. As Fig. 4 shows, recoveries near to 100% were obtained when the solvent volume was increased to 7 mL, mainly for MAL, DIA and PHO. Therefore, this volume was chosen as elution solvent and was used in the following experiments.

3.3.2. Optimization of sample pH and sample ionic strength

Sample characteristics, such as pH and salts content can affect the interactions between analytes and MCM-41 sorbent.

Fig. 4. Mean recovery (%) of the target pesticides obtained in the selection of the elution solvent and in between parentheses the solvent volume.

Sample pH is always an important factor in sorption processes of analytes with acidic-basic properties because it defines the molecular state of the compounds (ionic or neutral). In this study, only PEN, DIA and CYM show acidic-basic properties with pKa values of 1.5, 2.6 and 9.3, respectively. Thus, the effect of sample pH was evaluated in the range of 2.0–10.0 but extreme pH values were not considered due to the possible hydrolysis of some pesticides. The retention of the pesticides on the MCM-41 sorbent was studied by passing 50 mL of ultrapure water (in triplicate) spiked with 100 ng of each pesticide at different pH values adjusted with HCl 0.1 M or NaOH 0.1 M, through cartridges packed with 50 mg of MCM-41.

The results obtained are shown in Fig. 5a, where it can be seen that recoveries were no pH dependent for PEN, DIA, PMT and PHO, whereas, CYM showed the best recoveries (65%) at pH 2 which decreased drastically when the sample pH was higher to 4. As for the rest of pesticides, their recoveries decreased to almost 10% at pH 8 or higher for MET and they decreased to 80% for METH and drastically until 26% for MAL when the sample pH increased up to 10, probably due to a degradation process at high pH values. The same behavior was found for MAL in a previous work using MWCNTs as SPE sorbent [27]. Therefore, pH 2 was selected as the optimum value for further studies.

Next, the effect of the sample ionic strength (salts content) on the extraction process was checked. 50 mL of ultrapure water samples (in triplicate) adjusted at pH 2.0 ± 0.1, containing 100 ng of each pesticide and amounts of KCl ranging between 0.001 and 0.02 mol L⁻¹ were pre-concentrated onto 50 mg of MCM-41. Fig. 5b shows that recoveries were slightly affected by the salt content, in such a way that they increased slightly for MET, CYM and METH with the concentration of KCl or more significantly for PEN and then, this parameter decreased at a KCl concentration of 0.02 mol L⁻¹, being this diminution slight for MET, METH, MAL, DIA and PHO and very significant for CYM. The increase in the pesticide retention can be explained by the engagement of water molecules in the hydration spheres around the ionic salt, thus reducing the water available to dissolve the analytes (salting out effect) and the diminution can be due to the electrostatic interaction between the polar analytes and the salt ions, which reduces their capacity to be retained on the sorbent [11]. Therefore, the content of KCl was fixed at 0.01 mol L⁻¹ KCl.

3.3.3. MCM-41 amount

Aliquots of 100 mL of ultrapure water (in triplicate) spiked with 100 ng of each analyte were pre-concentrated through 50, 75 and 100 mg of MCM-41 following the optimized SPE procedure. Fig. 6 shows that the recoveries increased significantly for the three most polar pesticides (MET, CYM and METH) when the sorbent amount increased from 50 to 100 mg, whereas increased slightly or remained constant for the rest of pesticides. Therefore, 100 mg of MCM-41 were

selected for the SPE of the pesticides when using 100 mL of water samples. Larger amounts of MCM-41 were not checked because the flow rate decreased considerably, involving high pre-concentration times and higher costs.

3.3.4. Effect of sample loading volume or breakthrough

The water sample volume is an important parameter which reflects the retention capacity of the sorbent and it is related to the enrichment factor. Thus, the water sample volume was studied over the range of 25–250 mL. Results showed (Fig. 7) that only the recovery of the most polar pesticides MET and CYM (water solubility 55,000 and 780 mg L⁻¹, respectively) decreased when the sample volume was increased. The diminution on recoveries was directly related to the

Fig. 5. Mean recovery (%) of the target pesticides and the corresponding error bar (RSD, %) obtained in the optimization studies of: (a) the sample pH and (b) the salt content of the water sample.

Fig. 6. Mean recovery (%) obtained using different MCM-41 amounts on the pre-concentration of selected pesticides with an ultrapure sample volume of 100 mL.

pesticides polarity, being drastic for MET between 25 and 50 mL of water and slight for CYM in the same interval. This behavior of MET was also described by other authors [34] when they tested a newly synthesized copolymer based on N-vinylimadazole (a hydrophilic monomer) and divinylbenzene, as sorbent for the SPE of polar analytes. As a compromise, a volume of 100 mL of water sample allowed to obtained satisfactory recoveries for the target pesticides, except for MET whose recoveries were not adequate in any case.

3.4. Method validation

To determine the applicability of the proposed SPE-microflow LC-QqLIT-MS method in the analysis of the target compounds in real water samples, matrix effect, linearity, detection (LOD) and quantitation (LOQ) limits, precision and recovery were established for each pesticide.

3.4.1. Linearity and matrix effect

The linearity of the chromatographic response of pesticides was tested by using five standard calibration solutions by triplicate. The response was linear with the pesticide concentration between 0.10 and 10.00 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for DIA and between 0.10, 0.50 or 1.00 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (depending on the compound) and 75.00 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for the rest of pesticides, with determination coefficient of linear regression model (R^2) higher than 0.99 in all cases (Table 1).

However, the chromatographic response of the analyte in the sample extracts can change compared with the analyte response in the solvent due to the matrix effects. These effects may occur principally when other compounds co-elute with the analyte of interest and they are caused by numerous factors, including sample matrix, sample preparation procedure, quality of chromatographic separation, mobile phase additives and ion suppression (the major drawback for the analyst). Therefore, when matrix effects are present, the detection capability, repeatability and accuracy of the analytical method are affected.

Fig. 7. Recovery (%) of the target pesticides obtained in the water sample volume study.

In LC-MS/MS, matrix effects depend strongly on the type of ionization source, being ESI more prone to such effects than atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) [35]. In ESI sources, droplets are produced and a greater amount of additives (from eluents or sample matrices) may decrease evaporation efficiency and reduce the ability of analytes to reach the gas phase [36], leading to signal suppression. In some cases, it is also possible to observe an enhancement in the response of the analytes but ion suppression is much more frequent in LC determinations.

In order to study the matrix effect (ME), calibration curves were established using pesticide standards prepared in blank river extracts and blank dam extracts and both were compared with the corresponding solvent based calibration curve according to the equation:

$$\text{ME}(\%) = \left(\left(\frac{\text{Slope (matrix matched curve)}}{\text{Slope (solvent based curve)}} \right) - 1 \right) \times 100$$

The ME (%) values obtained for each pesticide are shown in Table 1, where it can be observed that most pesticides exhibited soft ($\leq 20\%$) and medium (20–50%) ME in both environmental waters and only DIA showed strong ME ($>50\%$) in dam water. Therefore, matrix effects should be considered to ensure that precision, selectivity and sensitivity will not be compromised [37].

Taking into account the drawbacks of the different strategies existing to overcome the matrix effect, the standard addition can be considered the most suitable approach to compensate for ion suppression as it also copes with the variability between samples [38]. Thus, in the following studies the standard addition method was used for pesticide quantification to overcome unavoidable matrix effects in real samples.

3.4.2. Detection and quantitation limits

Instrumental detection and quantitation limits (IDL and IQL) were established by analyzing pesticide standards in acetonitrile:water (10:90, v/v) at low concentrations. The IDL was determined as the minimum concentration of analyte giving a signal-to-noise ratio of 3 ($S/N = 3$) for the SRM2 transition, whereas the IQL was determined as the lowest concentration of pesticide whose SRM1 transition presented a $S/N = 10$. The IDLs attained for all pesticides were ranged from 0.02 to 0.25 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and the IQLs were ranged from 0.07 to 0.93 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Table 1). The IDLs and IQLs for MET, CYM, PMT and PHO are significantly higher than the ones corresponding to the other pesticides, which is in agreement with the low intensity of the two transitions (SRM1 and SRM2) for CYM and PMT and with the low ratio SRM2/SRM1 for CYM and PHO (Fig. S1 and Table S2).

The method detection limit (MDL) and the method quantitation limit (MQL) in river and dam water samples were estimated using the above S/N criteria but by analyzing blank samples extracts spiked at low concentrations of pesticides for both environmental water samples.

Table 1
Validation parameters in solvent and river and dam sample SPE extracts.

Pesticide	Linear range ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	R^2	Solvent		Blank river extract		Blank dam extract		River extract	Dam extract
			IDL ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	IQL ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	MDL ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	SQL ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	MDL ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	SQL ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	ME (%)	ME (%)
MET	0.10–75.00	0.993	0.04	0.07	0.50	2.35	0.61	2.50	30	27
CYM	1.00–75.00	0.996	0.19	0.93	3.52	9.50	5.10	16.14	8	9
METH	0.10–75.00	0.995	0.02	0.08	0.18	0.45	0.14	0.31	11	14
MAL	0.10–75.00	0.992	0.02	0.07	0.36	1.31	0.47	1.46	31	7
PEN	0.10–75.00	0.992	0.02	0.09	0.45	2.68	0.39	1.78	26	19
DIA	0.10–10.00	0.999	0.02	0.08	0.06	0.25	0.03	0.16	33	67
PMT	1.00–75.00	0.997	0.25	0.92	0.95	4.52	0.47	4.20	20	36
PHO	0.50–75.00	0.998	0.16	0.29	0.37	1.22	0.36	1.20	16	26

Table 1 shows MDLs ranging from 0.06 to $3.52 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in river water extracts and from 0.03 to $5.10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in dam water extracts. As for the SQLs (Table 1), the values achieved in river water extracts were ranged from 0.25 to $9.50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and in dam water extracts from 0.16 to $16.4 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.

On the other hand, the MDLs and SQLs in river and dam blank extracts are higher than in solvent, the higher values corresponding to CYM and PMT. This increase can be attributed to the strong ME for PMT and to the low sensitivity for CYM (which shows low ME). In addition, the MDLs and SQLs are similar in both river and dam blank extracts.

Taking into account that the pre-concentration factor (PF) achieved by the SPE-MCM-41 procedure was 100, the MDLs in the water samples were $\leq 0.01 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and $\leq 0.05 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for all pesticides, respectively (with the exception of CYM in environmental waters, which showed MDLs and SQLs equal or lower than 0.05 and $0.16 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively).

3.4.3. Accuracy and precision

The accuracy and precision of the proposed method were calculated in both environmental samples spiked at two concentration levels (0.05 and $0.10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for DIA and 0.10 and $0.20 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for the rest of pesticides) and by triplicate. The quantification of the pesticides was carried out using the standard addition method because matrix effects varied between samples [39].

In the accuracy study, three aliquots (100 mL) of each environmental water sample were spiked with $0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of each pesticide (DIA $0.05 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and then were pre-concentrated following the optimized SPE method.

For each water sample, two different amounts of the standard solutions of the pesticides were added to two of the obtained SPE extracts, in such a way that the concentrations of added analytes in the three sample extracts were 0, 0.10 and $10.00 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Next, these solutions were analyzed using the microflow LC-QqLIT-MS method and the concentration of each pesticide in each spiked sample was calculated by extrapolation. In addition, this experiment was conducted in the same way, but spiking the two kinds of environmental water samples with $0.2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of each pesticide ($0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for DIA). For precision issues, all recovery experiments were carried out in triplicate.

The results obtained (Table 2) showed that most of the pesticides are satisfactorily pre-concentrated into the MCM-41, with recoveries between 65% and 126% ($RSD \leq 14\%$), except for MET with recoveries lower than 30%. Recoveries obtained in environmental waters are in the same order than the ones obtained in ultrapure water, which demonstrated the usefulness of the MCM-41 as sorbent to pre-concentrate pesticides with low and intermediate polarity.

These results are similar or better than the ones obtained by us in a previous work [27], using MWCNTs as sorbent, except for the very polar MET which recoveries were slightly better with MWCNTs sorbent. This indicates that an alternative approach using hybrid organic-inorganic silica based mesoporous material should be checked as sorbent to improve the recoveries of the problematic very polar pesticides.

3.5. NMR studies

With the aim of justifying the similar and moderate recoveries obtained for the polar CYM (67–78%) and the less polar PHO (65–83%), NMR studies were carried out.

Solid-state NMR has shown to be useful to investigate mesoporous silica-based systems [40]. Here, ^{13}C nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) with cross polarization and magic angle spinning (CP/MAS) was applied to two different MCM-41 samples, each one containing CYM or PHO after their pre-concentration by SPE. These two analytes showed low recoveries (see Table 2) probably due to the low retention of the very polar CYM and to the insufficient elution of the less polar PHO.

The two $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ CP/MAS NMR spectra are shown in Fig. 8 evidencing clear signals associated with the pair MCM-41/PHO (Fig. 8a), but no signals associated to the pesticide were detected in the case of the pair MCM-41/CYM (Fig. 8b). The resonances located at δ_c 21.5, 26.0, 43.5 and 65.1 ppm, fit reasonably well with the chemical shifts found for PHO in the liquid state [41], which confirms the retention of this pesticide inside the pores of the mesoporous material. The two carbon signals observed at δ_c 30.4 and 32.3 ppm, were attributed to remains of the templating agent which was not thoroughly eliminated of the MCM-41 material [42], and they were found in both samples. Unfortunately, neither the aromatic nor the carbamate carbonyl signals of PHO were located in the spectrum, probably due to the difference in mobility for these moieties when trapped in the mesoporous, situation that has been noted previously in MCM-41 systems [40].

To confirm this selective behavior of MCM-41 against CYM and PHO, diffusion NMR in solution was performed. This methodology, and in particular, the one based on PGSE (Pulse Field Gradient Spin Echo), has been successfully applied to the study of the vast group of porous media [43], MCM-41, among them.

For instance, the diffusion behavior of linear and cyclic alkanes confined in mesoporous MCM-41 materials have been studied by this technique and showed that the thickness of the surface layer inside the

Table 2
Mean recoveries (%) and RSD (%) obtained in ultrapure, river and dam waters using standard addition calibration.

Pesticide	Mean recovery (RSD)*					
	Ultrapure water		River water		Dam water	
	$0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	$0.2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	$0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	$0.2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	$0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	$0.2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$
MET	15 (3)	18 (2)	16 (5)	17 (4)	29 (5)	21 (6)
CYM	77 (4)	72 (5)	67 (9)	72 (7)	72 (12)	78 (8)
METH	90 (5)	94 (6)	97 (14)	116 (10)	106 (10)	98 (7)
MAL	83 (6)	87 (4)	113 (10)	118 (6)	108 (6)	109 (5)
PEN	95 (4)	91 (5)	118 (12)	113 (11)	126 (7)	100 (8)
DIA ^a	90 (5)	93 (4)	121 (13)	118 (9)	92 (8)	105 (7)
PMT	89 (7)	85 (6)	114 (10)	92 (8)	113 (6)	116 (5)
PHO	83 (5)	80 (3)	75 (8)	72 (7)	70 (6)	65 (7)

^a 0.05 and $0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ * RSD (%) in parentheses, $n = 3$.

Fig. 8. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ CP/MAS NMR spectra of the: (a) MCM-41/PHO system and (b) MCM-41/CYM system.

pores is approximately one molecular layer for the adsorbates assayed [44].

The diffusion coefficient (D), which is sensitive to the size and shape of the molecular species, can be derived from the diffusion NMR experiments [45–47].

The hydrodynamic radii, r_H , were calculated using the Stokes-Einstein equation:

$$r_H = \frac{kT}{6\pi\eta D}$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant, T the absolute temperature and η the solvent viscosity.

Fig. S3 and S4 (in ESM) show Stejskal-Tanner plots from the ^1H PGSE diffusion measurements, which were used for D calculations.

As the observed resonances in the ^1H NMR spectra of a pesticide in the presence of MCM-41 are an average of free and bound (to MCM-41) species, the smaller the D value, the larger the hydrodynamic radius of the effective diffusing species would be, due to its interaction with the MCM-41 support. When this situation occurs, the obtained D is called as apparent diffusion coefficient.

Table 3 shows D and r_H values of CYM and PHO, with and without the presence of 20 mg of MCM-41 inside the NMR tube, in a $\text{D}_2\text{O}/\text{CD}_3\text{CN}$ (1:1, v/v) mixture adjusted to pD 2.0.

The D values of PHO and CYM in absence of MCM-41 were 0.5219 and $0.6864 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively, which yielded r_H of 4.7 and 3.6 \AA , respectively. In the case of PHO, the presence of MCM-41 significantly decreased the D value (apparent D) with a ΔD of $0.0349 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and a Δr_H of 0.4 \AA , which necessarily involve an adsorption of the analyte onto the mesoporous material. This effect is slightly reduced (ΔD of $0.0299 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) when the concentration of PHO is increased probably due to a larger excess of not-adsorbed PHO, which makes the average apparent D -value to some extent higher.

In the case of CYM, the presence of MCM-41 did not produce a significant increment on its diffusive properties (ΔD $0.0011 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and therefore almost no adsorption onto the mesoporous material is deduced.

As mentioned before, since no signals were observable for MCM-41 in solution, and assuming a rather large size for the MCM-41 compared to the pesticides under study, the observed difference on the apparent D value for PHO compared to CYM when there is MCM-41 sorbent inside the NMR tube, allowed us to establish a higher affinity of the MCM-41 for PHO than for the CYM.

4. Conclusions

SPE cartridges packed at the laboratory with 100 mg of MCM-41 were used to pre-concentrate height pesticides (organophosphorus, carbamates and triazole) in environmental water samples. Owing to

Table 3

Diffusion coefficient (D) and hydrodynamic radius (r_H) values for pesticide PHO and CYM with and without mesoporous material.^a

Entry		Conc. (mM)	D ($10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) ^b	r_H (\AA) ^c
1	PHO	35 (6.4 mg)	0.5219	4.7
2	CH_3CN		1.8357	1.4
3	H ₂ O		1.8980	1.3
4	CYM	35 (3.5 mg)	0.6864	3.6
5	CH_3CN		1.8714	1.3
6	H ₂ O		1.8835	1.3
7	PHO	35 (6.4 mg)	0.4942	5.0
8	MCM-41	– (20 mg)	^d	
9	CH_3CN		1.7691	1.4
10	H ₂ O		1.9380	1.3
11	PHO	3.3 (0.6 mg)	0.4870	5.1
12	MCM-41	– (20 mg)	^d	
13	CH_3CN		1.8005	1.4
14	H ₂ O		1.8370	1.4
15	CYM	6.1 (0.6 mg)	0.6749	3.7
16	MCM-41	– (20 mg)	^d	
17	CH_3CN		1.8633	1.3
18	H ₂ O		1.8929	1.3

^a The signals used for monitoring the intensity attenuation were δ_H 1.53 ppm for PHO, and δ_H 3.25 and 1.10 ppm for CYM. In brackets are given the milligrams used for each pesticide and MCM-41.

^b The experimental error in the D values is $\pm 2\%$.

^c The viscosity η used for the mixture $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{D}_2\text{O}$ was $0.8712 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

^d Not detected in the NMR spectra.

the large specific surface area and high adsorption capacity of MCM-41, relatively high extraction efficiency was found for most analytes.

The pesticides were analyzed by microflow LC-QqLIT-MS at ultra-trace levels. The SRM mode allowed the identification and quantification of those analytes presenting SRM2/SRM1 > 0.3 . Besides, when the SRM2 or was present at low intensity, the IDA mode allowed reliable identification at low concentration levels.

The standard addition method overcame matrix effect, which allowed satisfactory recoveries for the analytes in the spiked river and dam water samples.

Solid and solution NMR confirmed an affinity of the MCM-41 for non-polar pesticides such as PHO higher than for polar ones (for example CYM), thus explaining the low recoveries obtained for both of them, probably due to the low retention of CYM and the insufficient elution PHO.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material

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